

SENSORFINT: European Network for assuring food integrity using non-destructive spectral sensors

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COST Actions are competitive projects funded by the European Cooperation in Science and Technology (COST) organisation with the main objective of promoting the creation of research networks in innovative areas and facilitating the collaboration between academia and industry in Europe and beyond. The COST Action entitled *European Network for assuring food integrity using non-destructive spectral sensors* (SENSORFINT) is focused on the creation of a vibrant and multidisciplinary network, within the EU, in relation to non-destructive spectral sensors to generate and disseminate knowledge about these emerging and innovative technologies and their application for the real-time, in situ control of critical quality, safety, authenticity, and performance attributes for raw and in-process food materials, i.e., in the entire food chain. This network will increase the transfer of knowledge from academia to industry, boosting the implementation of spectral sensors within the food industry and, therefore, improving European food industry competitiveness.

To address these objectives and challenges, the project is structured in the five following Working Groups: 1. NDSS for the innovation in process control and labelling in the European food industry; 2. Innovation related to the integration of several NDSS signals for critical issues in food integrity; 3. Novel mathematical algorithms and methods for processing NDSS in real time; 4. Use of information and communication technologies (ICT) in building decision support systems for the industrial implementation of NDSS; 5. Dissemination and exploitation. This is an open network, so people working in related areas are welcome to join us.

Keywords: non-destructive spectral sensors, NIRS, hyperspectral, food integrity, networking opportunities

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REFERENCES

SENSORFINT MoU. 2019. <https://www.cost.eu/actions/CA19145/#tabs|Name:overview>

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